

Environmental Communication of Climate Change: Sure Means of Purposeful Compliance to Environmental Sustainability in Nigeria: A Study of River and Kogi State

Babatola Elijah Wale^a, Saliu Abubakar Feyidare^b, Jegede D.O^c

^{a&b}Department of Geography, Federal University Lokoja, Nigeria.

^cDepartment of Geography, Kogi State University, Kabba, Nigeria.

bebabatola@ksukabba.edu.ng

PAPER KEYWORDS

Environmental-communication
Sustainable-environment
Climate-change Mitigation
Adaptability

ABSTRACT

A sustainable environment is germane to profound life activities and existence; the only tool for knowledge and awareness of maintaining a sustainable environment is environmental communication. This, of course, is rooted in disseminating tangible information about the purposeful sustainability of our environment. This study, therefore, is concerned about environmental communication of climate change to the public; a high percentage of the Nigerian population is still defiant to the reality of climate change. If knowledge about climate change is not acquired and mitigation and adaptation principles are not applied, our environment as well as our lives are subject to vulnerability and consequently unsustainable. Data from previous related works were reviewed, focusing on the impact of climate change, adverse effects, and vulnerability. Qualitatively analysed. The study sensitises and opens the insight of the public to the possible mitigating behaviours to the environment and adaptable lifestyles to forestall the effects of climate change on the environment, as well as human activities and existence. A conclusion was made that environmental communication, if proactively used and implemented according to policy, would go a long way to reconstruct a sustainable environment in Nigeria.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19874282>

1.1. Introduction

Environmental communication refers to how information about the environment is shared between the government, scientists, NGOs, media, and the public to promote awareness, attitude change and sustainable behaviour. Adekeye (2011) defined climate change as " the generally observable prolonged alteration in global weather patterns resulting in temperature increases, storm activity, flash floods, drought and rising coastal water levels as polar ice melts because of global warming. Climate scientists have generally agreed that the climate is changing and these changes are largely caused by human activities. Global warming, which has now become synonymous with climate change, is the measurable increase in the average temperature of the Earth's near-surface air, ocean and land masses since the mid-20th century (Encarta, 2008). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) concluded that most of the

observed temperature increases since the mid-20th century in the atmosphere resulted from human activities such as fossil fuel burning and deforestation (Wikipedia, 2010).

Climate change is leading to increased average temperatures, more frequent heatwaves and increased heat stress in many parts of the world (Perkins-Kirkpatrick and Lewis, 2020; Schwingshackl et al., 2021). At predicted rates of global migration, one third of the population is expected to live in regions with average annual temperatures of >29 °C by 2050, with heat stress expected to increase twice as fast in cities as in surrounding rural areas by the mid-21st century (Xu et al., 2020; Wouters et al., 2017). Research shows that improvements to infrastructure (e.g. green space, bodies of water, improved airflow, building orientation, insulation) at a household level, in public places, and in indoor workplaces can lead to higher thermal comfort in hot climates (Haddad et al., 2020; Jay et al., 2021; Turek-Hankins et al., 2021; Adnan et al., 2022; Lo et al., 2022).

Daily temperatures are influencing human beings' daily lives in many ways. Exposure to extreme heat has been associated with higher mortality (Huang et al., 2012; Guo et al., 2017) and morbidity (Bi et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2018). Resulting heat stress and heat strain can also lead to mental (Noelke et al., 2016; Thompson et al., 2018) and occupational health issues (Spector et al., 2019; Borg et al., 2021), compromise workforce productivity (Zander et al., 2015; Flouris et al., 2018; Parsons et al., 2022) and decrease cognitive performance (Chen et al., 2020). Extended exposure to extreme heat can also increase aggression and crime (Heilmann et al., 2021), which can compromise general well-being and social life (Carter et al., 2020; Oppermann et al., 2021). Chronic disease conditions such as renal health (Borg et al., 2017), diabetes (Xu et al., 2019) and respiratory diseases such as asthma (Khalaj et al., 2010) are often exacerbated by hot weather.

Climate change at the rate we have been experiencing is detrimental, unsustainable, and affects the public in a multitude of ways; however, it does not affect every community the same way. Climate change disproportionately affects marginalised communities, which is known as environmental racism (Millar, 2023). Environmental racism is related to systemic racism in that it occurs as a result of policies and practices put in place by the organisation in power. Evidence of environmental racism is strong when looking at global warming, or more specifically, heat islands.

Extreme events are projected to become more frequent and intense under future climate scenarios all over the world (Almazroui et al., 2021; IPCC, 2022; Jones et al., 2022; Kirchmeier-Young et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019). Extreme events not only affect the health and well-being of individuals directly (e.g., heat strokes due to extreme heat, physical injury due to floods or wildfires), but also indirectly through impacts to the built environment and the surrounding landscape. Indirect consequences of extreme events may include exposures to water- and airborne-contaminants accidentally released from contaminated sites and hazardous waste facilities ("sites/ waste facilities"). For example, hurricanes may flood and impact Superfund sites where remedies are in progress (U.S. EPA, 2022a).

Literature Review

Climate Change Impact and Vulnerability

Studies show that the vulnerability of individuals and the human population to climate risks, including flood hazards, is dependent on several factors, including the geographical location, exposure of population and infrastructure, socio-economic and cultural conditions, political and institutional structures, as well as coping and adaptive capacity that differentiate the impacts on people and the human system (Wisner et al. 2004; Barroca et al. 2006). However, the sources of vulnerability are greatly associated with societies' patterns of development, and small investments in reducing risk can have disproportionately large positive impacts in protecting communities from harm. Vulnerability is therefore known to change significantly with social or habitat changes.

The combination of factors that shape vulnerability could be examined under three broad categories of vulnerability indicators, which include exposure, susceptibility, and coping indicators. With reference to flood vulnerability, Messner and Meyer (2006) identified two categories of exposure indicators. The first relates to the exposure of the element at risk in terms of proximity to a river, elevation of the area and frequency of floods, while the second category focuses on general flood characteristics like duration, velocity, inundation depth, and sedimentation load. Other exposure indicators described as flood hazard variables used to estimate the actions of floods on individuals include water depth rise rate, wave characteristics, and water temperature (Jonkman and Kelman 2005). Susceptibility indicators, on the other hand, measure the sensitivity of an element being confronted by a hazard and may include, in a narrow sense, measuring the impact of inundation depth and flood duration on buildings. It is observed, for example, that different types of buildings are impacted differently by floods. Also, the awareness and preparedness of affected people regarding the risk faced before the flood, their capability to cope with the hazard during a flood, to withstand its consequences and to recuperate after the flood event are all indicators of susceptibility. Coping indicators include general information on age, gender, education, poverty, institutional development, and proportion of vulnerable population, e.g., children and the elderly.

Necessity of Environmental Communication

Understanding and communicating possible spatial patterns of extreme events, potential contaminant releases, and subsequent exposures—especially to sensitive populations—is critical for local decision-makers to assess and consider as communities prepare for and recover from extreme events.

Two strands of quantitative literature are relevant for the context at hand. First, quantitative modelling approaches such as risk assessment methodologies (e.g., WHO, 2021a; U.S. EPA, 2022b) provide critical information on the frequency and magnitude of community exposures to potential contaminant releases. These studies consider site/waste facility information along with meteorology and environmental conditions to estimate contaminant releases into air and water and resulting human and ecological exposures and health risks. Although the probability and potential impacts of such events can be simulated using refined modelling techniques, communities, especially smaller, disadvantaged ones, may face resource and time constraints in implementing such methods. Also, a few risk assessment studies designed to explicitly consider future climatic conditions are described in the literature.

Second, screening methods that use quantitative indicators can be applied to inform decision-making and serve as reliable measures for evaluating progress toward goals (Janetos and Kenney, 2015). In the past, indicators have been used in the United States to assess and effectively communicate potential climate change issues in a wide range of contexts such as public health, forestry, agriculture, infrastructure, water management, community vulnerability, and resilience (Anderson et al., 2021; CSTE, 2018; Janetos and Kenney, 2020-2021; U.S. EPA, 2021a; USGCRP, 2018; Wilbanks et al., 2020). Indicators have also been applied to assess vulnerability to different hazards across the world (Contreras et al., 2020). However, indicator studies that focus specifically on vulnerabilities of sites/waste facilities to extreme events and their impacts on communities are limited. Previous indicator efforts on sites/waste facilities provided measures to assess the performance of municipal waste systems, but most have focused on recycling and landfill use (e.g., Greene and Tonjes, 2014). The U.S. EPA (2021b) provides measures for hazardous waste quantities, the number of cleanup sites, and municipal solid waste generation, but does not incorporate a broad set of sites/waste facilities and extreme events under changing climates.

The National policy on the Environment of 1989, later reviewed in 1999, also has as its major thrust, 'raising awareness. Owens-Ibie (2002:28) notes that these are consistent with the Rio resolution that noted that countries of the world should 'facilitate and encourage public awareness and participation by making environmental information widely available'. In spite of the existence of these provisions and efforts to create environmental awareness, the behaviour and attitude of most Nigerian does not reflect a deep understanding of possible steps to be taken in resolving, or at least, managing the environmental problem, since it involves finding a safe balance between man and his environment. This is why there is a need for consistent undertakings of research in this aspect, to curb the menace perpetrated in the environment by the public.

Adaptation and Mitigation

There are many definitions of adaptation and mitigation. However, we shall confine ourselves to the definitions provided by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). The 2007 IPCC report defines adaptation as: " Adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities". By adaptation, efforts are made to deal with the effects of climate change by coping with its negative impacts.

Adaptive capacity is most simply comprehended in terms of a certain system's ability to adapt, in order to cope with a specific climate hazard or combination of hazards. A territory, a community, a home, an economic sector, a corporation, a demographic group or an ecological system are all examples of systems. The combination of climatic hazard (examples, a drought, wind storm or extreme rainfall event) with the qualities of an exposed system - its sensitivity or socially constructed vulnerability - results in a certain consequence (Adger and Kelly, 1999; Pelling and Uitto, 2001; Brooks, 2003).

In comparison, mitigation of climate change refers to the reduction of greenhouse gases (GHG) in order to reduce climate change, such as global warming, which is caused by the emission of GHG. Simply put, mitigation deals with the causes of climate change by removing GHG. It is noteworthy that both mitigation and adaptation are interlinked.

That notwithstanding, in terms of risk management, the more successful 'Plan A' - which is mitigation, is the less 'Plan B', that is adaptation.

Adaptation and mitigation are two strategies used in combating the impact of climate change. Adaptation refers to actions taken to manage the effects of climate change. Since houses contribute greatly to greenhouse gas emissions, design decisions can equally help in reducing greenhouse gas emissions from houses. Similarly, the design of houses can provide adequate solutions that can reduce risks of damage from climate change. Both the mitigative and adaptive measures can be achieved through sustainable Architecture or (green architecture). Mitigation, on the other hand, refers to planned activities aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions and lessening demand on nature. Environmental communication intends to provide the public with the rich knowledge of the above, because understanding the two concepts will aid the public to be sensitive to the need to mitigate and so adhere to policies that would facilitate mitigation, thereby lessening the rigours and challenges of Adaptability.

According to Agbeja & Taiwo (2010), climate change mitigation within and around Gebu Forest Reserve will be influenced most positively by FMP (Forest Management Plan) with the highest odds ratio of 162943E6. This is followed by GFR (Governance of Forest Reserve) and PF (Provision of Funding) with odds ratios of 54091.37 and 1.82, respectively. The higher the odds ratio, the more influential the institutional measures will be on Climate Change Mitigation within and around Gebu Forest. The study stated further that institutional measures are needed for climate change mitigation within and around the Gebu Forest Reserve, Kogi State.

1.2. Research Methods

Data for this research were sourced from previously published related research in the study area, that is, the secondary data. Analyses were basically confirmative, inductive narration and explanation of the data to either confirm or refute the subject matter contents of the research objectives.

1.3. Results and Discussion

Indispensability of Environmental Communication

Environmental communication, which actually means the process by which information about Environmental issues is disseminated to the public, probably by various means. The United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) conference held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 underscored the need for awareness creation on the environment. Agenda 21 of this meeting identified, among other things, the need to develop public education and awareness programmes (UNCED, 1992). Public education and awareness are one of the main processes of environmental communication, according to the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP).

A study carried out by Ayotunde and Melvin (2009) on climate change and the perception and attitude of Nigerian youths in Ile-Ife, South Western Nigeria, gives a picture of the level of awareness on climate change. Out of a total of three hundred and fifty (350) respondents, 144 (41%) reported previous awareness of climate change, while the majority, 162 (68%) of the respondents, noted that they are not aware of climate change.

44 representing 13.7% of the respondents called climate change 'another gimmick'. The conclusion of this study is that active education of the populace about the subject matter should be given attention for enhanced management of climatic risk. Nkporoku, A.K. et al. (2022); in his study in River state, Public perceptions of climate change revealed that Combat measures suggested included: 21.6%: sensitisation and awareness campaigns, 17.9%: controlling deforestation, 18.9%: improved governance

Ali, A. & Isah, S. (2024); Kogi State — Environmental Communication & Perceptions; Cultural Livelihoods & Environmental Impact. A community study (n = 120) exploring cultural livelihoods (e.g., farming, fishing, festivals) found 56% of these livelihoods are nearing extinction. Held that: 78% of participants saw a high negative environmental impact, 57% saw moderate negative social impact, 51% noted political implications.

Reality of Climate change and its vulnerability

In Adelekan (2010), “I thought the rain was a child’s play when it began. I said to myself that it would stop before daybreak when I would go to work, but before I knew what was happening, my room was flooded. I feared that the world was coming to an end. My only consolation was God’s assurance that He would not destroy the world with a flood again. I had never experienced such in my life”. - Resident, Abeokuta (Source: Saturday Punch, August 4, 2007).

According to Adelekan (2010), the Abeokuta 2007 flood disaster reflected the vulnerability of residents of affected areas arising from their socio-economic characteristics, exposure and susceptibility indicators, and the failure of the relevant institutions to ensure social protection of the people. This is because the risk profile of citizens and disaster victims depends largely on the organisations that serve them and regulate civil life (Hewitt 2007). A substantial proportion of damages to individuals and infrastructure could have been prevented or avoided if adequate measures were taken or regulations enforced. Greater commitment is therefore required on the part of governments and relevant institutions in the aspect of disaster prevention and risk management.

The disastrous flood event in Abeokuta, the impact of which extended southward along the course of the Ogun River into areas in Lagos State, underscores the need to actively put in place structures and institutions for effective flood risk reduction and management in Nigerian urban areas.

Adelekan (2010). At the household level, the impacts of floods on the social and economic well-being of household members are evident. Flood water, a mix of drainage, surface run-off and sewage, flows into many houses, sometimes reaching waist height. Most respondents (91 per cent) in all four communities noted recurrent visits to health centres because of ill-health and an increase in medical expenses as a major outcome of floods. In addition, potable water shortages, which may be due to water pollution and damage to water pipes following flood events, were noted by 94.5 per cent of respondents. In terms of economic/livelihood activities, 85.6 per cent of respondents in the four communities indicated that flood events denied them job opportunities, while 8.8 per cent noted that floods disturbed their economic activities. Because the majority of the population in these communities depends on wages from daily work, any restrictions on

economic activities as a result of floods make them highly vulnerable.

An impact of flooding in these poor urban communities that is worth noting relates to the mental health of residents. Respondents in the different communities noted that as a result of the annual flooding of their communities, they lived in perpetual fear of future flood events and the possible outbreak of an epidemic. The consequences of this included loss of peace of mind, the inability to sleep well, loss of appetite, discouragement and a feeling of being neglected. This can lead to depression as the flood-affected population feels helpless due to the overwhelming impacts. The mental health aspects and consequences of repeated flooding can therefore be far-reaching, difficult to cope with, and call for some consideration in the planning of formal responses.

Also, Nkporku, A. K. et al. (2022); Public Perceptions of Climate Change, Conflict & Migration. In a survey of 400 households across Rivers State, 90.7% of respondents recognised that the climate has changed over time. Of these, 26% attributed it to human activities, while 25.3% saw it as an “end-time phenomenon.” Notably, 60% of farmers reported climate change impacting crop output. Adesina & Onyema (2022): Overall Sustainable Development Awareness. In a broader survey of Rivers State residents (n ≈589), Climate change awareness: 82.5%, Ozone layer depletion: 70.7%, Urban air pollution health effects: 81.8%, Rapid land-use change: 66.1%, Forest depletion impacts: 67.2%, Concerns about low protection for biodiversity: 68.9% disagreed that it was secure.

Ensure the lifestyles that are human-adapted and environmentally sustainable.

The fact that 73% of the respondents largely favoured the construction of drainage systems as an adaptation measure indicates the attitude of the community, which is aware of the provision of adequate drainage infrastructure in the successful management of water and consequent flooding in Lokoja, Kogi State, in Bamidele & Richard (2024). There is an opportunity to integrate climate change risk reduction into the urban development of Lagos as more coastal settlements emerge, learning from the current vulnerability of the urban poor population. A range of measures to increase the adaptive capacity of the urban poor that governments at different levels should pursue include: restrictions on land reclamation activities in newly developing areas, management and environmental education for citizens, etc. Adelekan (2009).

Geographic and climate data indicate: Annual rainfall: 1,100–1,300 mm; rainy season from April to October. Notably, between 2001 and 2014, built-up areas increased by ~10.7%, with 31% of farmers adjusting planting dates, 22% adopting different crop varieties, and 21% using other adaptation strategies in response to rainfall changes in Kogi State Wikipedia, (2025).

1.4. Conclusion

The study, in its findings, buttresses the fact that there is still a need for more knowledge for the people of Nigeria about the connection between the environment and climate and the progressive effects of the population's environmental activities on climate change. In the study of cultural livelihood in Kogi State, 78 % have a perception of a high negative environmental impact; they are vulnerable because of a lack of awareness. Considering the level of environmental awareness in Ile-Ife, Osun State, in 2009, the

suggestion of the need for Sensitisation awareness and perceptual impact due to Environmental communication in Kogi State in 2024.

Also, there were facts about the reality of climate change, ranging from flood disasters in Adelekan to the impact on farming in Nkporku et al. The research reveals that the public should be aware of climate change realities and adopt adjustable lifestyles that are adaptable to a sustainable environment and life.

Rivers State demonstrates variable awareness across communities, but generally a high level of environmental recognition, albeit with gaps in effective communication and behaviour outreach.

Kogi State, on the other hand, shows adaptive behaviour among farmers, likely driven by changing rainfall patterns and climate variability. Communication data is more indirect, tied to cultural practices and adaptation strategies. It is therefore an onerous task for all agencies involved in communication matters to increase their level of communication strategies about climate change to the public, for the lives and environmental sustainability.

1.5. References

- Adelekan, I. O. (2010): Vulnerability of poor urban coastal communities to flooding in Lagos, Nigeria, *Journal of Environment & Urbanisation, International Institute for Environment and Development (IIED)*, Vol. **22(2)**: 433-450.
- Adelekeye, O.O. (2011): Mitigating the Effects of Climate Change through Sustainable Building Environment Agenda IV. *Seminar proceedings organised by the Architects Registration Council of Nigeria*, April, 2011.
- Adesina, O.& Onyema, E. (2022); Effect of Population growth on sustainable development in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 6(12), 112-121.
- Ali, A., & Isah, S. (2024). Community perception on the effect of cultural livelihoods on the environment in Kogi State, Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sustainable Development*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/386376685_Community_Perception_on_the_Effect_of_Cultural_Livelihoods_on_the_Environment_in_Kogi_State_Nigeria.
- Agbeja, B.O. & Taiwo, O.J. (2010); Impacts of Abandoned Gebu Forest Escarpment Reserve in Kogi State of Nigeria on Climate Change: Need for Forest Institutional Measures. *Nigeria Journal of Ecology*, Vol. **11**; Pp20-28.
- Anderson, S.M., Heath, L.S., Emery, M.R., Hicke, J.A., Littell, J.S., Lucier, A., Masek, J.G., Peterson, D.L., Pouyat, R., Potter, K.M., Robertson, G., Sperry, J. (2021).

Developing a set of indicators to identify, monitor, and track impacts and changes in forests of the United States. *Clim. Chang.* 165 (1–2), 13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-021-02993-6>.

Bamidele, J.O. & Richard, K. (2024): Impact of Adaptive strategy in urban flood management, in Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Convergent and Informatic Science Research (IJCISR)*, Vol. 6, No. 9 Pp35-42.

Barroca B, Bernardara P, Mouchel JM, Hubert G (2006); Indicators for identification of urban flood vulnerability. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst Sci* 6: 553–558. Available from www.nat-hazards-earth-systsci.net/6/553/2006/.

Bi, P., Williams, S., Loughnan, M., Lloyd, G., et al. (2011). The effects of extreme heat on human mortality and morbidity in Australia: implications for public health. *Asia Pac.J. Public Health* 23, 27S–36S.

Climate Change Subcommittee (2018); Environmental Health Indicators: *Climate Change*. <https://www.cste.org/page/ehindicatorsclimate> (accessed 18 February 2022).

Contreras, D., Chamorro, A., Wilkinson, S. (2020); Review article: the spatial dimension in the assessment of urban socio-economic vulnerability related to geohazards. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 20 (6), 1663–1687. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-20-1663-2020>

Encarta (2008): DVD, Redmond, WA, Microsoft Corporation, 2008. U.S.A

Guo, Y., Gasparri, A., Armstrong, B.G., Tawatsupa, B., Tobias, A., Lavigne, E., et al. (2017); Heat wave and mortality: a multicountry, multicomunity study. *Environ. Health Perspect.* 125, 087006.

Huang, C., Barnett, A., Wang, X., et al. (2012). The impact of temperature on years of life lost in Brisbane, Australia. *Nat. Climate Change* 2, 265–270.

Anetos, A.C., Kenney, M.A. (2015). Developing better indicators to track climate impacts. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* 13, 403. <https://doi.org/10.1890/1540-9295-13.8.403>.

Jonkman SN, Kelman I (2005); An analysis of the causes and circumstances of flood disaster deaths. *Disasters* 29(1):75– 97.

- Messner F, Meyer V (2006); Flood damage, vulnerability and risk perception: challenges for flood damage research. In: *Schanze J, Zeman E, Marsalek J (eds) Flood risk management-hazards, vulnerability and mitigation measures, Nato science series.* Springer, New York. Available at http://www.ufz.de/data/Disk_Papiere_2005-132647.pdf
- Nkporbu, A. K., et al. (2022). Perception of the public on climate change, natural resources, migration and conflict in River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, **6(8)**,152–160. <https://rsisinternational.org/virtual-library/papers/perception-of-public-on-climate-change-natural-reosurces-migration-and-conflict-in-rivers-state-nigeria/>.
- U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. EPA), (2022a); Superfund Climate Resilience. <https://www.epa.gov/superfund/superfund-climate-resilience> (accessed 18 February 2022).
- U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. EPA), (2022b); Human Health Risk Assessment. <https://www.epa.gov/risk/human-health-risk-assessment> (accessed 10 January 2023).
- U.S. Global Change Research Program USGCRP), (2018); Impacts, Risks, and Adaptation in the United States: *The Fourth National Climate Assessment*, vol. II. U.S. Global Change Research Program, Washington, DC.
- Wilbanks, T., Zimmerman, R., Julius, S., Kirshen, P., Smith, J., Moss, R., Solecki, W., Ruth, M., Conrad, S., Fernandez, S. Matthews, M., Savonis, M., Scarlett, L., Schwartz Jr., H., Toole, L., (2020); Toward indicators of the performance of US infrastructures under climate change risks. *Clim. Chang.* *163* (4), 1795–1813. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-020-02942-9>.
- Wikipedia, (2010): Sustainable Architecture www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/sustainable_architecture
- Wikipedia contributors. (2025). Kogi State’s Climate Context & Adaptation Awareness. In *Wikipedia*. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kogi_State.
- WHO (2021a); WHO Human Health Risk Assessment Toolkit: Chemical Hazards, *second edition*. *World Health Organisation* (IPCS Harmonisation Project Document, no. 8), Geneva.

Wisner B, Blaikie P, Cannon T, Davis I (2004); *At risk: natural hazards, people vulnerability and disasters, 2nd edn. Routledge, London.*

Zhang, Y., Beggs, P.J., Bambrick, H., et al. (2018); *The MJA-Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: Australian policy inaction threatens lives. Med. J. Aust. 209,474.*